

DEVELOPMENT OF MULTISCALE DAMAGE PROPAGATION ANALYSIS METHOD FOR WOVEN LAMINATES USING A HOMOGENIZATION THEORY

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Background

- For analyzing damage propagation behavior for woven composite, one of the effective approaches is a unit cell analysis which can explicitly consider microstructures.
- The behavior is influenced by types of woven fabrics and uncertainty of the microstructures, e.g. laminate misalignment (LM).
- The analysis domains are so large that enormous computational costs are required.
- We have to develop the method of reduction in the analysis domain of woven composites considering the microstructures.

Purpose of this study

- Novel unit cells (blue lines) smaller than previous ones (orange lines) and boundary conditions for homogenization analysis are proposed and a failure criterion is introduced into the theory.
- The damage propagation analyses of plain-, 2×2 twill- and 5H satin-woven glass fiber-reinforced plastic (GFRP) composites with several LM under on-axis uniaxial tension are conducted.
- Effects of the LM on the microscopic damage behavior and macroscopic strength of the woven composites are examined.

Reduction in analysis domain of 2×2 twill woven composites

Equilibrium of microscopic stress

$$\int_A \hat{\sigma}_{ij} v_{i,j} dA - \int_{\Gamma} \hat{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma = 0$$

Unit cell A

$$\int_{\Gamma} \hat{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma = 0$$

Setting Periodicity and Point-symmetry as boundary conditions

In the in-plane direction

In the thickness direction

Laminate misalignment (LM)

Hoffman's failure criterion (1967)

$$F = C_1(\sigma_T - \sigma_Z)^2 + C_2(\sigma_Z - \sigma_L)^2 + C_3(\sigma_L - \sigma_T)^2 + C_4\sigma_L + C_5\sigma_T + C_6\sigma_Z + C_7\tau_{TZ}^2 + C_8\tau_{ZL}^2 + C_9\tau_{LT}^2$$

Judgment of failure of elements in fiber bundles and matrix material.

Failure expression and damaged stiffness matrix (Zako et al., 2003)

Determination of damage modes of the elements.

Damage mode	Fiber bundle						matrix
	L	T	LT	Z	ZL	TZ	L-TZ
Stress to strength ratio	$\frac{\sigma_L^2}{F_L^L F_L^C}$	$\frac{\sigma_T^2}{F_T^L F_T^C}$	$\left(\frac{\tau_{LT}}{F_{LT}^S}\right)^2$	$\frac{\sigma_Z^2}{F_Z^L F_Z^C}$	$\left(\frac{\tau_{ZL}}{F_{ZT}^S}\right)^2$	$\left(\frac{\tau_{TZ}}{F_{TZ}^S}\right)^2$	Calculate in the same manner as fiber bundles

Homogenization analysis for woven composites

Equilibrium of microscopic stress

$$\int_A \hat{\sigma}_{ij} n_j v_i d\Gamma = 0$$

Microscopic constitutive equation

$$\hat{\sigma}_{ij} = c_{ijkl}(\dot{\epsilon}_{kl} - \Delta T \alpha_{kl})$$

Microscopic velocity field

$$\dot{u}_i(y,t) = \dot{E}_{ij}(t)y_j + \chi_{ij}^{kl}(y,t)\dot{E}_{kl} + \Delta T \psi_i$$

Boundary value problems (BPs)

$$\int_A c_{ijpq} \chi_{p,q}^{kl} v_{i,j} dA = - \int_A c_{ijkl} v_{i,j} dA$$

$$\int_A c_{ijpq} \psi_{p,q} v_{i,j} dA = \int_A c_{ijkl} \alpha_{kl} v_{i,j} dA$$

Input [C] and resolve BPs

Macroscopic constitutive equation

$$\hat{\Sigma}_{ij} = \langle c_{ijkl}(\delta_{pk}\delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \rangle \dot{E}_{kl} - \langle c_{ijkl}(\alpha_{kl} - \psi_{k,l}) \rangle \Delta T$$

Localization ↑ Incremental analysis ↓ Homogenization

$$[C] = \begin{bmatrix} d_L^2 C_{11} & d_L d_T C_{12} & d_L d_Z C_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & d_T^2 C_{22} & d_T d_Z C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & d_Z^2 C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & d_{TZ} C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & d_{ZL} C_{55} & 0 \\ & & & & & d_{LT} C_{66} \end{bmatrix}$$

Stiffness of the elements is reduced.

Analysis conditions

Analysis models and the number of LM considered in this study

Plain-woven nodes: 2499 elements: 2048 (LM patterns: 13)	2×2 twill-woven nodes: 4899 elements: 4096 (LM patterns: 23)	5H Satin-woven nodes: 12099 elements: 10240 (LM patterns: 10)
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Material constants (Uetsuji et al., (2007), Kaddour and Hinton (2013))

Fiber bundles : E-glass / Vinyl ester: transversely isotropic elastic materials,
Volume fraction of fiber bundles = 44 [%]
Matrix : Vinyl ester: isotropic elastic material

Analysis procedure

1. Thermal residual stress analysis

Loading conditions : macroscopic stress $\Sigma_{ij} = 0$ (composites can freely deform)
Temperature conditions : $\Delta T = -80$ [K] (From a curing temperature to a RT)

$\sigma_{ij}^{thermal}$, recalculate stiffness matrix [C]

2. Damage propagation analysis

Loading direction : y_3 -direction at constant strain rate $\dot{E}_{33} = 10^{-3}$ [1/s]
Final strain : $E_{33} = 2.0$ %

Results of analysis

Macroscopic stress – strain relations of the woven composites with LM

Microscopic damage distributions at fracture strains of the woven composites with LM

